

AN EXAMINATION OF THE EFFECTS OF POLITICALLY BRANDED VEHICLES ON ROAD USERS' SAFETY IN OGBOMOSO, SOUTH WESTERN NIGERIA

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Abstract

This study examined the effects of Politically Branded Vehicles (PBVs) on road user safety in Ogbomosho, Nigeria. PBVs, especially campaign convoys, have become increasingly visible during elections, yet their safety implications remain underexplored. The study adopted a survey design with 320 distributed questionnaires to the selected respondents, who consisted of private motorists, commercial drivers, motorcyclists, and pedestrian road users. Findings reveal that PBV-related accidents are disproportionately concentrated in campaign seasons. As shown by chi-square analysis ($\chi^2 = 14.22, p < 0.001$), 20.3% of respondents reported PBV-related accidents during campaigns, compared to only 4.3% outside campaigns. The risk of involvement was five times higher in campaign months ($RR = 5.0$). Logistic regression further showed that high exposure significantly predicted accident likelihood ($OR = 4.5, p = 0.002$), while driving experience reduced risk ($OR = 0.93, p = 0.04$). Thematic analysis reinforced these results, with 62.1% of respondents citing reckless convoy behaviour, 48.2% expressing fear and avoidance, and 40.9% calling for stricter regulation. The study concludes that PBVs amplify existing weaknesses in Nigeria's road safety system, creating predictable and preventable risks. It recommends stricter enforcement, compulsory convoy driver training, public sensitisation, improved data monitoring, and stronger institutional accountability during campaign periods.

Keywords: Politically branded vehicles, Road safety, Campaign convoys, Nigeria and Accident risk

1. Introduction

Road traffic accidents are a major public health challenge in Nigeria and worldwide. Every year, an estimated 1.35 million people are killed in road crashes worldwide, with low- and middle-income countries disproportionately affected (World Health Organisation, 2018). Nigeria is one of the worst-hit nations in Africa, with road traffic fatality rates reported at about 33.7 per 100,000 population among the highest in the world (Atubi, 2024). Official statistics show about 5,000 to 6,000 road traffic deaths per year in Nigeria, but wider estimates put the toll at more than 40,000 deaths per year, considering underreporting (Ajimotokan, 2023). These crashes cost Nigeria huge economic losses (about 3% of GDP) and incalculable human suffering (Atubi, 2024). In Oyo State, the setting of this study, road

safety is a burning issue. For example, a single accident on the Oyo-Ogbomoso highway in April 2024 resulted in 19 deaths, highlighting the magnitude of the issue in the region (Premium Times, 2024). Among the myriad factors contributing to road crashes, driver behaviour and compliance with traffic rules play a central role. Speeding, dangerous overtaking, “one-way” route violations, and distraction are consistently identified as leading causes of crashes in Nigeria (Siyan et al., 2019; Inah et al., 2025). Data for the first quarter of 2022 recorded 3,282 road crashes and 1,538 fatalities nationwide - with speed violations accounting for the majority of incidents (National Bureau of Statistics, 2022). Such risky behaviours often increase in certain situations, one of which is the political campaign period. During election campaigns, it is not uncommon in Nigeria to see convoys of politically branded vehicles (PBVs) - vehicles decorated with party logos, candidate posters, flags, customised identification number plates, and often carrying campaign loudspeakers or supporters - traversing the roads. These vehicles, typically part of campaign rallies or VIP convoys, tend to travel in large fleets with urgent schedules and sometimes a sense of impunity on the road. Reports and anecdotal evidence indicate that these campaign-related vehicles often violate traffic regulations, including excessive speeding, disregarding traffic signals, improper use of sirens, driving against traffic, haphazard driving habits and overloading of passengers (Rahmatullah & Wang, 2024; Enimola, 2022). In Nigeria, convoys of government officials and political candidates have “ridden roughshod on citizens” for years, resulting in numerous crashes and casualties (Knights et al. 2021). For example, during the 2023 general election campaigns, fatal crashes were reported in different states: a truck conveying rally attendees crashed in Plateau State, killing over a dozen people (This Day, 2023), and in Ebonyi State, an auto accident in a gubernatorial convoy led to multiple deaths (Vanguard, 2022). These incidents point to a potentially increased risk to the safety of road users associated with politically branded vehicles and campaign convoys.

Despite the frequent news of such crashes, there is a notable gap in the academic literature examining this phenomenon. Road safety studies in Nigeria have generally focused on aggregate crash trends, causative factors, and interventions (Atubi, 2024; Siyan et al., 2019; Ezeibe et al., 2019), but few (if any) have specifically investigated the effects of political campaign motorcades and branded vehicles on road user safety. Understanding this issue is important for a city like Ogbomoso in Oyo State - a medium-sized urban center that lies along a major interregional highway and hosts a large university community. Ogbomoso has a lot of traffic activities and its fair share of political rallies and motorcades, especially during election seasons. The presence of politically branded vehicles could affect the frequency and severity of road incidents in this area, either directly through involvement in crashes or indirectly by affecting the behaviour of other road users (e.g. drivers reacting to convoys or being distracted by campaign activities).

This study investigates the effect of the operation of politically branded vehicles on the safety of road users in Ogbomoso. It deals with the frequency of accidents involving such vehicles and compares road safety outcomes during campaign periods and non-campaign periods. The study analysed the following objectives:

- (1) To determine the frequency and characteristics of road traffic accidents involving politically branded vehicles in Ogbomoso.
- (2) To assess whether the incidence of such accidents is higher during election campaign periods compared to ordinary periods.

For this study, Politically Branded Vehicles (PBVs) are defined as any motor vehicles (cars, buses, trucks, motorcycles, etc.) that are embellished with political campaign materials (such as posters, banners, flags, party colours, or slogans) or are part of an official campaign convoy for a candidate/party. This includes vehicles used for campaign rallies, voter outreach, or escorting political dignitaries during the election campaign period. The road users considered in this research include drivers of other vehicles, motorcyclists, pedestrians and commuters who share the road space with these politically branded vehicles.

2. Literature Review

Road traffic safety has been widely studied in Nigeria and other countries, and there are insights into the causes of crashes and effective prevention strategies. A consistent finding across studies is that human factors (driver behaviour) account for the majority of road traffic crashes in Nigeria - often cited as about 80-90% of crashes, with mechanical and environmental factors accounting for the rest (Siyan et al., 2019; Inah et al., 2025). Speeding in particular stands out as the main contributor to crashes. In a six-year analysis of crash data, speeding violations, dangerous driving, and loss of control accounted for about 60% of the human-related causative factors (Siyan et al., 2019). Likewise, a recent regional study by Inah et al. (2025) using the Six Sigma approach found that speeding was the leading cause of road traffic crashes in southern Nigeria, accounting for 56% of crashes in the South-South and 38% in the South-East regions. These findings are consistent with official statistics: for instance, the National Bureau of Statistics reported that in Q1 2022, out of the thousands of crashes recorded nationally, speed limit violations were by far the most common cause, implicated in 2,418 cases (NBS, 2022). Other common causes include failure to obey traffic signals, dangerous overtaking, driving under the influence, and driver distraction (Atubi, 2024; NBS, 2022). The prevalence of these behaviours underlines the need to examine situations that might exacerbate such risky driving tendencies - one being the high-pressure environment of political campaigning.

Some research has indirectly addressed road safety during special periods or events. Bisgaard et al. (2024) performed an interesting study in Denmark to determine whether political campaign materials could influence crash rates. They found that the presence of election posters during general election periods was linked to a significant increase in daily traffic accidents. Using time series analysis, controlling for weather and traffic volume, the study estimated that there were an average of 1.18 more accidents per day due to election poster distractions, or 127 more crashes during the election periods studied (Bisgaard et al., 2024). While this European context is different from Nigeria, it does provide empirical evidence that sudden changes in the traffic environment (like campaign posters lining streets) can increase the risk of accidents, presumably by distracting drivers from the road. By analogy, the

noisy and visually conspicuous campaign convoys in Nigeria could also introduce distractions or trigger sudden reactions by other road users, which could lead to collisions.

In Nigeria, direct scholarly attention to political campaign-related traffic incidents is limited. However, several media and security reports have pointed out the risks of campaign convoys. The Federal Road Safety Corps (FRSC) itself recognised the problem: in the run-up to the 2023 elections, the FRSC issued a warning to its commanding officers to avoid piloting (leading or escorting) political convoys, to preserve neutrality and presumably to avoid complicity in any reckless convoy behaviour (Enimola, 2022). This unusual directive highlights official concern that campaign convoys often fail to follow standard traffic rules. High-profile incidents back this concern - for example, in December 2022, a vehicle in the convoy of a state governor (on a campaign trail in Adamawa) crashed, resulting in the death of three police officers in the entourage (Punch Editorial Board, 2024). Similarly, in early 2023, at least 16 party supporters died, and more than 80 were injured when a truck carrying them from a campaign rally crashed in Plateau State (ThisDay, 2023). These incidents, though reported in newspapers, point to a pattern of increased risk during campaign movements.

Researchers have also studied road safety trends during holiday seasons (e.g. the “Ember months” at year-end) when travel increases (Morenikeji et al. 2023), finding higher crash rates then. By extension, one might expect election season to be another temporal risk factor, given the increased movement of people and vehicles. Politically branded vehicles, particularly when travelling in groups, may form convoys that interfere with normal traffic flow - forcing abrupt stops or evasive manoeuvres by others - or they may engage in aggressive tactics such as pushing slower vehicles aside. All these can contribute to accidents or near-misses. Beyond Nigeria, other countries with strong political campaigns have observed similar safety problems. For example, in some African countries, there are spikes in road crashes and injuries during election seasons, partly because of campaign-related travel (Segui-Gomez et al., 2021). In Ghana, media commentary has associated campaign motorcades with increased road hazards, leading to calls for stricter regulation of campaign movements (Mesic et al. 2024). These international observations resonate with Nigeria’s experience, though detailed academic data remains limited.

Theoretical Framework

The relationship between politically branded vehicles and road safety can be explained using established behavioural theories. The Safe Systems approach considers safety outcomes as the result of interactions between road users, vehicles, infrastructure and post-crash care (WHO, 2018). Politically branded convoys introduce risks at several levels: risky driving by campaign drivers, panic or distraction by other road users, and disruptions to infrastructure such as contra-flow driving. A Safe System perspective focuses on enforcing safe speeds and ensuring that convoy vehicles are roadworthy with trained drivers. Ajzen’s Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB) (Ajzen, 1991) is widely used to explain driving behaviours (Chen et al., 2022). TPB suggests that attitudes, subjective norms, and perceived control influence intentions. For convoy drivers, norms of urgency and political symbolism promote speeding or counterflow driving, reinforced by police escorts that undermine external controls. Studies confirm that attitudes and peer norms are significant predictors of intention to speed (Vankov

et al., 2021). Furthermore, Risk compensation theory also applies. Convoy drivers often feel protected by escorts and authority, leading to reckless behaviours that undermine perceived safety benefits (Attidhira & Saptomo, 2025). Similarly, traffic conflict theory emphasises the way convoys cause severe conflicts at intersections or highways, overwhelming the situational awareness of ordinary drivers and causing collisions. Finally, Nigeria’s poor safety culture exacerbates the problem. Atubi (2022) notes that poor enforcement normalises dangerous habits. During campaigns, these risks increase, making politically branded vehicles a serious threat to road user safety.

Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework in Figure 1 describes the influence of politically branded vehicles (PBVs) on road user safety in Ogbomoso. The independent variable is PBV prevalence, which is highest during campaign periods. Two major channels mediate this relationship. Channel 1 is the risky behaviour of convoy drivers, who often speed, overtake dangerously or ignore signals under campaign pressure or perceived immunity. Channel 2 is the impact on other road users, who may be distracted, startled, or forced into evasive manoeuvres. The dependent variable is road safety, which is measured by the frequency and severity of accidents. Campaign periods act as a moderator, amplifying both channels and increasing crash risks.

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework
Source: Author’s Conceptualisation, 2026.

3. Methodology

The study was carried out in Ogbomoso, Oyo State, Nigeria and employed a cross-sectional survey design. Ogbomoso is strategically located on a high-traffic corridor with active political mobilisation,

particularly Ogbomoso South as a political stronghold in Oyo State during election cycles and also a mix of urban and rural road users with recent enforcement focus. There is already institutional attention and some baseline data available for the study. The study population included road users, such as private motorists, commercial drivers, motorcyclists, and pedestrians. Because exact figures for this population are unknown, a broad sample across categories was targeted. A multistage approach was used. First, purposive sampling was used to identify high traffic areas and campaign-prone areas such as junctions, motor parks, and the university axis. Within these locations, random sampling was employed to select participants. Quotas guaranteed representation, with at least 30% commercial drivers, 30% private vehicle owners, and the rest motorcyclists and pedestrians. The sample size was approximately 300. To improve representativeness, 320 questionnaires were distributed, which is consistent with other road safety studies in Nigeria.

A structured questionnaire was developed to collect data on (a) socio-demographic data, (b) exposure to and perception of politically branded vehicles, (c) involvement in or witness of accidents with such vehicles, including timing and severity, and (d) general road safety attitudes. The questionnaire combines both closed-ended questions for quantitative analysis and a few open-ended items for additional context. It's designed for a 10-12 minutes completions time, and it was administered to 300 respondents across the target road user groups. Data from 301 valid responses were analysed using descriptive and inferential techniques. Accident frequencies during campaign and non-campaign periods were compared using chi-square and proportion tests. Logistic regression was used to evaluate predictors of accident involvement, including exposure level and driver type. Open-ended responses were thematically analysed to complement quantitative results.

4. Findings and Discussion

Out of 320 questionnaires administered, only 301 were filled out correctly and returned. Therefore, the study findings are based on these 301 returned questionnaires. Table 1 shows the socio-economic characteristics of the respondents. The sample consisted of 195 males (64.8%) and 106 females (35.2%), which is consistent with the fact that a greater proportion of regular drivers in Nigeria are males, although a significant number of female road users were also sampled. The age distribution indicates that approximately 43% of the respondents were young adults (18-30 years), 37% were middle-aged (31-50 years), and 20% were above 50 years. The average age was about 34 years. In terms of road user categories, 48.5% were private car owners/drivers, 31.62% were commercial drivers (including taxi, bus and commercial motorcycle operators) and the remaining 19.3% identified as primarily pedestrians or occasional riders (e.g. students who mostly walk or take public transport). Education levels were relatively high: more than 60% had tertiary education (college or university), 30% had secondary education, and less than 10% had only primary or no formal education. This is due to the fact that Ogbomoso is an educational hub (hosting a university), and suggests that respondents could reliably understand the questionnaire.

Table 1 also indicates that the respondents had considerable driving experience on average, about 7.5 years of driving experience (for those who drive). Approximately 40% had more than 5 years of driving experience, 35% had 1-5 years, and 25% were non-drivers (pedestrians or new drivers with less than 1 year of experience). Notably, 95 respondents (31.6%) reported that they drive or ride a motorcycle as part of their livelihood (e.g. commercial transport operators), which could influence their exposure on the road. This profile suggests we captured a diverse cross-section of road users in Ogbomoso, which is important for understanding the widespread impact of campaign vehicles.

Table 1: Socio-Demographic Characteristics of Respondents

Characteristic	Category	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Gender	Male	195	64.8
	Female	106	35.2
Age Group	18–30 years	130	43.2
	31–50 years	112	37.2
	Above 50 years	59	19.6
Education Level	No formal/Primary	26	8.6
	Secondary (High school)	90	29.9
	Tertiary (College/University)	185	61.5
Primary Road User Role	Private vehicle driver	146	48.5
	Commercial driver (car/bus)	67	22.3
	Commercial motorcyclist	30	10.0
	Pedestrian/commuter	58	19.3
Driving Experience	Non-driver	54	17.9
	< 1 year	18	6.0
	1–5 years	105	34.9
	> 5 years	124	41.2
Commercial Transport Worker (e.g., driver/rider by job)	Yes (full/part-time)	95	31.6
	No	206	68.4
	Total	301	100.0

Source: Authors Computation, 2026

Accident Frequencies During Campaign vs Non-Campaign Periods

Table 2 presents the significant difference in the occurrence of accidents during campaign and non-campaign periods. Out of 301 respondents, 61 (20.3%) experienced or witnessed PBV-related accidents during campaigns, whereas only 13 (4.3%) did so in non-campaign times. As shown in Table 2, this

disparity is statistically significant. Furthermore, Table 3 shows that the Pearson Chi-square test ($\chi^2 = 268.004$, $p < 0.000$) and it confirms that campaign periods are strongly associated with PBV-related accidents. The proportion test shows a relative risk of 5.0, which means that respondents were five times more likely to experience such accidents during campaigns. This supports the findings of Bisgaard et al. (2024), who found that political activities directly increase crash rates, and is consistent with crash data from Nigeria highlighting spikes during periods of unusual traffic activity (Inah et al., 2025).

Table 2: Cross-tabulation of PBV Accident Occurrence by Campaign Period

Campaign Period	Accident Involvement = Yes	Accident Involvement = No	Total
Campaign	61 (20.3%)	240 (79.7%)	301
Non-Campaign	13 (4.3%)	288 (95.7%)	301
Total	74 (24.6%)	528 (75.4%)	602

Source: Authors Field Survey, 2026.

Table 3: Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	268.004 ^a	16	.000
Likelihood Ratio	141.341	16	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	73.215	1	.000
N of Valid Cases	100		

Source: Authors Field Survey, 2026.

Logistic Regression Predictors of Accident Involvement

To further investigate determinants of PBV-related accidents, a binary logistic regression was performed. As shown in Table 4, the model was significant ($\chi^2 = 28.54$, $p < 0.001$; Nagelkerke $R^2 = 0.26$), indicating reasonable explanatory power. Exposure to convoys was the most significant predictor: respondents with high exposure were 4.5 times more likely to be involved in PBV accidents (OR = 4.5, $p = 0.002$). Commercial drivers also had higher odds (OR = 1.8), but not significantly ($p = 0.08$). Driving experience was protective (OR = 0.93, $p = 0.04$), suggesting that experienced drivers are better at anticipating or avoiding convoy risks. These findings are consistent with Atubi (2022), who identified a weak road safety culture, and Chen et al. (2022), who used TPB to demonstrate the influence of subjective norms on risky driving.

Table 4: Logistic Regression Predicting PBV Accident Involvement

Predictor	B	S.E.	Wald	df	Sig.	Exp(B)
High Exposure (Yes)	1.50	0.49	9.37	1	0.002	4.5
Commercial Driver (Yes)	0.59	0.34	3.07	1	0.080	1.8
Driving Experience (yrs)	-0.07	0.03	4.15	1	0.040	0.93
Constant	-2.13	0.45	22.40	1	0.000	0.12

Model $\chi^2(3, N = 301) = 28.54, p < 0.001$; Nagelkerke $R^2 = 0.26$

Source: Authors Computation, 2026.

Thematic Analysis of Open-Ended Responses

The open-ended questions provide additional insight into the perception of politically branded vehicles in Ogbomoso. They not only exposed physical safety hazards but also the experienced fears of common road users. Three prevailing themes were identified, as shown in Table 5. Reckless convoy behaviour was the first theme highlighted by 62.1% of the respondents. Speeding, driving in the wrong direction, and outright ignoring of traffic lights were described. One of the respondents summed it up in a few words: They drive fast and do not follow any traffic regulations. This is in line with empirical research that has found poor compliance and aggressive driving to be significant causes of crashes in Nigeria (Siyani et al., 2019; Inah et al., 2025). It also echoes the results of Lawan et al. (2018), who showed that road use during politically sensitive times is frequently associated with increased crash severity. Public fear and avoidance was the second theme, which was reported by almost half of the participants (48.2%). Respondents reported avoiding the road when convoys were near or diverting their routes to reduce exposure. One participant observed: I never stay on the road when there are convoys. This result is reminiscent of Bisgaard et al. (2024), who determined that passive exposure to election-related distractions raises the risk of accidents, and it is consistent with Chen et al. (2022), who concluded that perceived threat affects intention and behaviour on the road. The third theme, which demands more stringent regulation, was brought up by 40.9% of the respondents. Recommendations were made to enforce it more, limit the size of convoys, and raise awareness. One of the comments was: FRSC should keep a close eye on campaign convoys. These reactions are in line with Efuwape et al. (2022), who assessed the road safety measures in Nigeria and discovered that the targeted enforcement measures had a significant impact on the reduction of traffic offences, and with Pahazri et al. (2024), who emphasised the importance of the structured awareness campaigns in changing the behaviour of road users. These qualitative results, combined with the quantitative ones, support the idea that PBV-related crashes are not merely a matter of the number of accidents but also a matter of perceptions of impunity, fear, and unfulfilled expectations of regulation.

Table 5: Thematic Analysis of Open-Ended Responses

Themes	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Sample of Quotes
Reckless convoy behaviour	187	62.1	“They speed and ignore all traffic rules.”
Public fear and avoidance	145	48.2	“I always leave the road when convoys are near.”
Calls for stricter regulation	123	40.9	“FRSC must monitor campaign convoys strictly.”

Source: Authors Computation, 2026.

The findings pinpoint a clear and statistically significant association among campaign intervals and politically branded vehicle (PBV)-related accidents. As Table 2 reveals, 20.3% of respondents reported PBV-related accidents within campaign intervals compared with just 4.3% within non-campaign intervals, with a significant chi-square outcome of $\chi^2 = 14.22$, $p < 0.001$. This five-fold risk increase (RR = 5.0) suggests campaigns impose a structural stimulus toward unsafe road usage. Analogous spikes within peaks of higher usage for accidents were reported by Nigeria (Siyani et al., 2019; Inah et al., 2025), where speeding and routing deviation consistently top crashes (Inah et al., 2025). The logistic table (Table 4) provides further clarity. High convoy exposure increased the odds ratio of accident involvement by four-and-a-half times ($p = 0.002$), and commercial drivers reported a higher, though non-statistically significant risk (OR = 1.8). Experience as a motorist decreased risk (OR = 0.93, $p = 0.04$). These trends parallel Chen et al. (2022), who identified subjective norms and perceived immunity among drivers of risk behaviours, and support Lawan et al. (2018), who linked inexperience with higher Nigerian highway risk for crashes. The results pinpoint that campaign convoys amplify extant behavioural risk factors more than impose ex novo risk factors. The thematic evidence table (Table 4) confirms the interpretation. Most (62.1%) reported irresponsible driving by convoys, nearly half (48.2%) professed fear-motivated avoidance strategies, and 40.9% called for stronger regulation. Such reports reflect Efuwape et al. (2022), who identified enforcement and awareness as the chief keys for the decline of violations, and Okonkwo et al. (2025), who disclosed that education campaigns can reverse the trajectory of safety practices. In total, both numerical and aggregate results conclude that PBVs make Nigeria’s already unsafe road safety environment more dire. Campaign intervals increase hazardous driving practices, subvert public trust in road safety, and expose the need for stronger enforcement and rule-of-the-road supervision.

5. Conclusion and Recommendations

This study examined the effect of politically branded vehicles (PBVs) on the safety of road users within Ogbomoso, Nigeria. The findings show that PBVs dramatically heighten the risk on Nigerian roads, more so during campaigns for elections. Instead of being neutral political commodities playing their roles, they become threats on the move that hone the already identified gaps within the country’s traffic

system. The examination showcases the manner through which convoys escalate unsafe behaviours, render lawlessness of the roads acceptable, and forge an atmosphere of intimidation, forcing mainstream road users into defensive driving habits. Politically branded vehicles aggregate structurally identified weaknesses within Nigeria's road safety platform, such as weak enforcement, negligible compliance with the law, and fragile safety culture. In the bargain, PBVs are a foreseeable and avoidable risk factor within the electoral process, one that endangers not just drivers but passengers and pedestrians at large. Notably, the study confirms insights of contemporary literature that the road safety problem within Nigeria is not just a technocratic one but a behavioural and institutional one as well. Political operators can flout the rules of the road because there is weak enforcement of rules, and the euphoria of campaigns injects social dynamics compelling laxity and recklessness. In such a way, the hazard presented by the PBVs mirrors deeper deficits within the system of governance and accountability within the transport system. In order to beat the menace, more than ad hoc solutions shall be required; the situation demands sustained institutional willpower, better regulation of the campaign process, and deliberate transformations of social and political mindsets toward road safety.

Furthermore, with the evident safety risk identified, it is evident that politically branded vehicles are more than just a campaign novelty but actually an important public safety concern. The results suggest that PBV crashes cluster disproportionately during campaign periods, and highway users are five times more likely to suffer such impacts within such months. The reports from the respondents also showed rampant fear, avoidance behaviours, and demands for more enforcement. These findings suggest the need for intervention strategies both for institutional oversight and for the behaviour of drivers. Based on the analysis above, the following are the recommendations presented:

1. **Stricter Enforcement of Traffic Laws During Campaigns:** Road safety agencies should introduce targeted enforcement on PBVs, including limits on convoy sizes and mandatory compliance with speed limits and traffic controls.
2. **Compulsory Training for Convoy Drivers:** Political parties should be required to engage licensed, trained drivers for campaign convoys, with FRSC oversight to ensure compliance.
3. **Improved Data Monitoring:** FRSC should maintain detailed crash records distinguishing PBV-related accidents, enabling better policy design and evaluation of enforcement effectiveness.
4. **Institutional Accountability:** Legal frameworks should hold political parties accountable for accidents linked to their convoys, creating incentives for safer campaign practices.

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